

Hegemony, Resistance, (Dis-)Order

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Introduction

Wars are critical junctures that disrupt existing orders. They signify a transformation from a recent past to a hitherto invisible future. The 2023-2025 Gaza War is such an event that will herald the emergence of a new regional order in the Middle East. The signs of the new order did not start with Hamas' attack on Israel on 7 October 2023 or with Israel's genocidal war on Gaza (UN, 2024). The first signal came in September 2024 when Israel detonated thousands of paggers held by Hezbollah members, conducted thousands of raids on Lebanon, and assassinated the movement's leader, Hassan Nasrallah (Bassam and Mackenzie 2024), effectively debilitating Hezbollah. This was followed on 8 December by the collapse of Bashar al-Assad's regime in Syria, which isolated Iran, eroding the Resistance Axis. These developments will pave the way for the U.S. to seek hegemony in the Middle East. But in practice, the absence of a legitimate resolution of the Arab-Israeli conflict will keep the region unstable and may generate resistance to U.S. and Israeli hegemonic ambitions.

Hegemony and Resistance

The erosion of the Resistance Axis and the emergence of the U.S. as a dominant power seals a long interlude: a century-old period between the British-French domination after the dismantling of the Ottoman Empire (1920-1952) and 2025. That period saw various attempts by regional powers, like Jamal Abdel Nasser's Egypt or Imam Khomeini's Iran, to challenge Western hegemonic strategies in the region, but one after the other faltered due to intra-regional rivalries and wars with Israel. Arab anti-colonial struggles, intra-regional rivalries, and wars offered Israel, the West's strongest ally, numerous opportunities to realize its goals. The 1967 Arab defeat against Israel dealt a fatal blow to Nasser's Cairo-based "Pan-Arab" regional order. The 1979 Camp David agreement returned the Sinai Peninsula to Egypt but neutralized it in the Arab-Israeli conflict. The Iraq-Iran war (1980-88) effectively neutralized two of the West's regional rivals.

After the collapse of the Soviet Union, Syria and Iran became the two middle powers that challenged U.S. hegemony in the region (Ehteshami and Hinnebusch 1997). Their support of Hezbollah, Islamic Jihad, and

Hamas gave them influence in the Arab-Israeli conflict. The failure of the Oslo Peace Process and Israel's withdrawal from Lebanon (2000) and Gaza (2005) consolidated the alliance and legitimized it in the eyes of many Arabs. The U.S. occupation of Iraq (2003-2011) and the rise of a predominantly Shi'a regime there offered Iran a strategic opportunity to connect Tehran to Beirut. In addition to its nuclear program, this plan, dubbed by its rivals as a "Shi'a Crescent," threatened Arab regimes and brought some of them (officially, UAE and Bahrain) closer to Israel.

But the weakening of the Resistance Axis started with the Syrian uprising that targeted Assad's regime in 2011 and pitted his regional allies against rivals in a protracted war that not only destroyed Syria but also undermined the power of Assad's regime and army. Iran and Hezbollah's intervention in support of Assad (and interferences in Iraq and Yemen) delegitimized and isolated the two actors in the region (Hinnebusch and Saouli 2020). When Hamas attacked Israel in 2023, the Resistance Axis was caught unaware; but to preserve its ontological security, Hezbollah engaged in 'constrained warfare' with Israel (Saouli 2024). Israel's attacks on Hezbollah in September 2024, akin to the fatal attack on the Egyptian army in 1967, have weakened Hezbollah (Mazzetti et.al, 2025). The fall of Assad has severed the geographical link between Hezbollah and Iran, curtailing Iran's strategic reach. In Syria, *Hay'at al-Tahrir* is in the process of regime building that, if successful, will diminish Iranian influence there. Its transitional leader, Ahmed Al-Shara'a, is a close ally of Turkey and is seeking recognition from the U.S. and its Arab allies in the region.

These developments offer the U.S. unprecedented influence in the region. Most regimes

in the region continue to depend on its military and economic support. In theory, the U.S. could establish hegemony and a regional order organized on the Westphalian principle of the territorial state secured by international law and, potentially, regional economic integration—a *pax Americana!* Such an order will secure U.S. interests, enable the pivot to China, and generate much-needed stability for a region that has suffered many wars and tragedies since its inception a century ago (Hinnebusch 2003; Stein 2021). The decline of irredentist and transnational projects, like Islamism and Arabism, may facilitate the transition to such a regional order.

A Multi-polar (dis-)Order?

However, this prospect is unlikely to materialize because of the Arab-Israeli conflict. The emerging regional order will be shaped by the U.S. and Israeli visions (which are not necessarily identical) *and* resistance to these visions by their adversaries. Having isolated Iran, pressure on which will increase from within and without, and debilitated the Resistance Axis, Israel now perceives a golden opportunity to realize its Zionist goals: a Jewish state over all the territory, including the West Bank and Gaza Strip. But Zionism will have to face the reality that has haunted it since its birth: what to do with the (7 million) Palestinians that live in Israel, the West Bank, and the Gaza Strip—let alone the Palestinian Diaspora. The genocide in Gaza, which made the tiny enclave uninhabitable for its 2.5 million inhabitants and will require decades to rebuild, has led President Trump, echoing the Israeli far-right, to make appalling proposals about transferring Gazans to Jordan and Egypt (Gritten 2025) or elsewhere. Simultaneously, Israel would focus on the annexation of the occupied West Bank. In this permissive regional order, Israel will attempt to become a

regional gendarme that deters, represses, and constrains threatening actors from Lebanon to Syria, Iraq, Iran, or Yemen.

But these attempts are likely to generate resistance, not least from Arab regimes whose stability and legitimacy would be threatened by Zionist goals. The decline of the Resistance Alliance will pit US/Israel against U.S. regional allies. Turkey, Egypt, Jordan, and Saudi Arabia have opposed US/Israeli plans for the Palestinians. The death of the two-state solution, which regional as well as international states see as the only viable solution to the Arab-Israeli conflict, will generate regional instability and might spark a new wave of uprisings if Arab regimes remain complacent about it. Such a scenario might draw new geopolitical fault lines bringing Arab regimes closer to Turkey (whose influence in Syria is growing) and Iran. Israeli incursions into Syria and Lebanon will test the legitimacy of their rulers; the absence of Israeli restraint might restore the conditions for armed resistance against it. Unlike the post-Ottoman era (1920-45), the emergence of these fault-lines might deepen the influence of U.S. rivals, Russia and China, in the region.

The choices actors pursue during critical junctures set trajectories that constrain their future behavior. In envisioning a new regional order that secures their interests, the U.S. and Israel might be creating a hostile, multipolar, and unstable order.♦

References

- Bassam, Laila and Mackenzie, James. 2024. "Hezbollah's tunnels and flexible command weather Israel's deadly blows". *Reuters* 27 September. Accessed online 13 February 2025.
- Ehteshami, Anoushiravan and Raymond A. Hinnebusch 1997. *Syria and Iran: Middle Powers in a Penetrated System*. London: Routledge
- Gritten, David. 2025. "Trump says no right of return for Palestinians under Gaza Plan". *BBC News*. Accessed 13 February 2025.
- Hinnebusch, Raymond and Adham Saouli. Eds. 2020. *The War for Syria: Regional and International Dimensions of the Syrian Uprisings*. London: Routledge.
- Hinnebusch, Raymond. 2015. *The International Politics of the Middle East*. 2. ed. Manchester: Manchester University Press.
- Mazzetti, Mark, Frankel, Sheera, and Bergman, Ronen. 2024. *Behind the Dismantling of Hezbollah: Decades of Israeli Intelligence*. New York Times. 29 December 2024. Accessed online on 12 February 2025
- Saouli, Adham. 2024. "Identity, Anxiety, and War: Hezbollah and the Gaza Tragedy", *Al-Muntaqa*. Vol.7. No. 1, pp. 99-114.
- Stein, Ewan. 2021. *International Relations in the Middle East: Hegemonic Strategies and Regional Order*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- United Nations. 2024. "UN Special Committee finds Israel's warfare methods in Gaza consistent with genocide, including use of starvation as weapon of war". UN Special Committee Report A/79/363. 20 September 2024. Accessed online on 12 February 2025.